

Radio Frequency Low-Cost Temperature Sensor

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Abstract— In this work, preliminary results regarding a radio frequency planar low-cost temperature sensor, with potential for sensing and communications integration, are described. The sensor is based on a ring resonator onto which a layer of PDMS is added as the sensor active layer, allowing resonant frequency shift according to varying temperature since the permittivity of the PDMS changes when exposed to different temperatures. The combination of a ring resonator with a layer of PDMS on top allows the development of a thermal sensor using microwave signals, such as those used for communications. The resonant frequency changes at a rate of 1.01 MHz per degree Celsius. The resonant frequency of the ring resonator at room temperature was designed to resonate at 3GHz. This work is proof of concept towards integrated sensing and communication components.

Keywords—PDMS; Ring Resonator; Sensor, temperature; VNA

I. INTRODUCTION

Ring resonators are widely used in microwave-based sensing applications for material characterization, including the detection of temperature-induced changes in dielectric properties [1]. Electromagnetic fields interact with materials, enabling the measurement of physical parameters across a broad frequency range. The microstrip ring resonator is a compact, cost-effective, and highly sensitive planar device extensively employed in communication systems, biomedical applications, and environmental monitoring [2]. Its operational principle is based on the propagation of electromagnetic waves along a conductive ring structure, generating standing wave patterns at specific resonance frequencies [2]. On the other hand, polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) is a material that enables wireless and chip-less electromagnetic sensing techniques, and thus allows for cost-effective and portable measurement setups, expanding practical applications [3].

The development of temperature sensors using PDMS and microwave circuits has seen significant advancements in recent years. PDMS, a versatile polymer, has become a popular material for temperature sensing applications due to its unique properties and compatibility with microwave technology. PDMS-based temperature sensors have been developed using various approaches [4]. One notable method involves the integration of PDMS with microwave circuits to create a capacitive dielectric temperature sensor. These sensors utilize PDMS loaded with conductive fillers such as copper, graphite, and milled carbon fiber powders [5]. These sensors have been successfully utilized in biomedical monitoring, automotive systems, and industrial environments where real-time and wireless temperature sensing is required [6].

This work focuses on a very low-cost and simple fabrication solution by embedding a PDMS layer directly on top of a microstrip ring resonator. The PDMS acts as the active sensing layer, its temperature-dependent dielectric properties enable temperature sensing. As the temperature changes, the dielectric constant of PDMS varies, leading to shifts in the resonance frequency response of the sensor. This effect forms the basis of the proposed PDMS-based ring resonator temperature sensor. By precisely measuring the frequency shift, accurate temperature monitoring can be achieved.

By leveraging the properties of PDMS within microstrip ring resonator structures, we have developed a very-low-cost temperature sensor with the scope of sensing temperature using microwave signals, such as those used for communications. This integration represents a promising approach for integrated communications and sensing, offering robust performance, ease of fabrication and integration with other components and subsystems.

The integration of PDMS as a sensing layer in ring resonators is believed to be performed for the first time. PDMS, known for its flexibility, thermal stability, and compatibility with microwave technology, has been widely utilized in various temperature-sensing applications, mainly at optical wavelengths. The combination of PDMS with microwave resonators, particularly ring resonators, is proof of concept towards integrated sensing and communication devices.

II. DESIGN AND RESULTS

The sensor in this work consists of a planar weakly coupled ring resonator made on a low loss substrate. A layer of PDMS is then cured directly on top of the resonator, as shown in Fig. 1.

Microstrip ring resonators typically consist of a circular or ring-shaped conductive strip on a dielectric substrate. The resonator operates based on the principle that electromagnetic waves propagate along the ring, creating standing wave patterns at specific frequencies [2].

In this work, the microstrip ring resonator is used to make a temperature sensor due to its high sensitivity and compact size, including the ease of integration of the PDMS active sensing layer, all patterned in one face of the substrate. The proposed temperature-dependent changes in the resonant frequency of the ring resonator are used to measure temperature variations.

The PDMS is placed on top of the ring resonator to sense temperature variations. The ring resonator was designed to resonate at 3 GHz with PDMS on top. Since the dielectric constant of PDMS changes with temperature, the resonant frequency of the resonator changes at a rate of 1.01 MHz per degree Celsius.

Fig. 1. Ring Resonator temperature sensor.

The automated experimental setup used to perform sensor characterization and measurements involves a thermal chamber and network analyzer controlled using MATLAB, as shown in Fig. 2. The first scattering parameter results obtained with this proof of concept are shown at -30 degrees and 60 degrees in Fig. 3, where a resonant frequency variation of 100 MHz is observed.

CONCLUSIONS

This work presents preliminary results on a proof-of-concept device for temperature sensing, the sensor circuit can

be potentially integrated in future 6G sensing and communication systems. Future work includes the development of higher sensitivity devices operating in the FR3 band.

Fig. 2. Temperature setup and chamber.

Fig. 3. Measurement results.

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